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**YOUTH LEISURE DURING COVID-19:
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The purpose of the article is to study the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the organisation of leisure of Ukrainian youth. The research methodology is based on a comprehensive analysis of the national system of actions to prevent the spread of coronavirus infection, implemented by the Ukrainian government; analytical, structural and logical, comparative methods that allowed us to consider the legal status, educational and leisure activity of young people in Ukraine, international experience of youth participation in social projects to counter the spread of COVID-19; the method of theoretical generalisation, used to summarise the results; cultural approach, which helped to identify factors of influence of national measures on the activities of cultural and creative industries. Scientific novelty. In this study, we present three creative initiatives of Ukrainian youth to organise their own leisure activities, which were launched during the lockdown and created on the basis of the rich potential of national cultural heritage and folk traditions. Conclusions. In response to the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ukrainian state has developed a system of measures to prevent it. Despite a large number of places for leisure, sports, and creative activities in Ukraine, lockdown restrictions and bans caused by COVID-19 led to their closure, and young people focused on leisure at home, creative self-development, and self-organisation of their free time. It is determined that the best international experience

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of youth activity in countering the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic is realised mainly in the social dimension. The young people of Ukraine do not stand aside from the global challenges of our time, but initiate unique creative developments under pandemic conditions. Ukrainian creative initiatives are presented, including the online project #GlobalLesyaUkrainka2021 and the successful experience of self-organisation of leisure activities by students of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts (Challenge#Lovnyamysto and Winter Magic Fest).

Keywords: COVID-19; youth leisure; Ukraine; creative projects, creative industries

Introduction

With the rapid spread of the COVID-19 pandemic from the beginning of 2020 to the present, the whole world is in a state of active turbulence. According to the UN Secretary-General, the most global crisis since World War II has affected not only the health sector on each continent but has also led to crises in education, culture, and the economy (UNESCO, 2020). In particular, culture and education were perhaps the first to feel the effects of the pandemic and face restrictions. The situation was so unprecedented that no one had the opportunity to use the experience of their predecessors to solve problems. However, even now, in difficult times for Ukraine, it is worth remembering the fundamental importance of creativity in the life of society — the preservation of culture as a means of informal interaction between people is extremely important for psychological comfort.

This large-scale challenge led to the introduction of a set of anti-epidemiological security measures, which, first of all, required saving lives both around the world and in each country, encouraged the search for new communication tools and the transition to online leisure, taking into account national characteristics, motivational needs and digital opportunities; required immediate action by state institutions and radically influenced the reformatting of public consciousness, which was expressed in the adaptation of humanity to a new way of life in the context of COVID-19.

Various pandemic restrictions have significantly affected all social groups, including young people, who belong to one of the most vulnerable groups, suffering from unemployment, lack of access to quality education, skills development, ethnic and gender discrimination, social protection and more. These and many other factors motivate young people not to be spectators of crisis social processes, but to act as stable and active agents and catalysts for change, for which COVID worked as a real-world scenario for ingenuity, creativity, integration and more. Because of this, the study of young people's use of creative approaches to their own leisure is relevant and requires an analysis of the best international and Ukrainian experience in this sector.

This research aims to contribute to the scientific literature and practice of leisure activities, complementing the understanding of the impact of the pandemic on youth leisure management at the national (Ukrainian) level. The study is based on the presentation, promotion and dissemination within Ukraine and abroad of creative forms of leisure for Ukrainian youth during the quarantine of 2020–2021.

Purpose of the article

The purpose of the article is to study the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the organisation of leisure of Ukrainian youth. The research methodology is a comprehensive analysis of the national system of actions to prevent the spread of coronavirus infection, implemented by the Ukrainian government, and their impact on the activities of the cultural and creative industries; an overview of the international experience of youth participation in social projects to counter the spread of COVID-19; a brief overview of the legal status, educational and leisure activities of young people in Ukraine in the period before the lockdown in 2020; an analysis of changes in the structure of youth leisure that occurred under the influence of the pandemic and acquired new creative forms of self-development and creative expression. Based on information sources and personal experience of the authors in the higher education institution, two creative projects initiated by students of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts to counteract the negative impact of the pandemic on the emotional and psychological state of Ukrainian youth are described, and the information on one of the largest and most creative flash mobs during the second wave of the pandemic #GlobalLesyaUkrainka2021, where active participants were young people not only from Ukraine but also from other countries, is provided.

Main research material

From the point of view of eyewitnesses of these events, we can state that the global challenges caused by the pandemic led to the introduction in Ukraine in March 2020 of strict quarantine (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2020), which was carried out in several stages, until May. Lockdown caused the transition of the country's residents to distance learning and work, suspended the subway, urban and interurban transport, led to the closure of physical spaces of leisure, culture, art, sports, catering and more. Mass cultural, entertainment, sports and other events were banned. The Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine has envisaged five stages for the gradual exit from quarantine, which lasted until 22 June 2020.

The first stage of easing quarantine restrictions, subject to anti-epidemic rules, began only on 11 May 2020 and contributed to opening parks, recreation areas, museums, libraries, etc. ("Pomiakshennia karantynu v Ukraini", 2020). The government's proposed adaptive quarantine measures have allowed restaurants to open summer terraces and playgrounds and takeaway cooking. Shopping and entertainment centres, beauty salons, gyms, fitness centres, religious organizations have worked with restrictions on the number of visitors. And only in June, provided compliance with the rules of social distancing (1 person per 5 square meters), temperature screening at the entrance to the institution, chess placement of visitors (with a distance of 1.5 m between them) could open cultural institutions (Holovnyi derzhavnyi sanitarnyi likar Ukrainy, 2020).

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 22.07.2020 №641 (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020a) established "green", "yellow", "orange", and "red" levels of the epidemic danger of COVID-19 spread in the regions of Ukraine. These levels were also introduced throughout 2021, depending on the epidemic situation in certain

administrative-territorial units or a particular region of Ukraine. The work of cultural institutions was allowed in the “yellow” and “green” zones, provided that no more than 50% of the seats were filled. Mass cultural events in the “orange” zone could take place with the participation of no more than 100 people. The strictest quarantine restrictions were in place in the “red” zone, including the closure of entertainment and cultural facilities.

The gradual resumption of the sectors of the creative industries, in particular: the organization of concerts, theatre performances, exhibitions, film screenings, became possible only in August 2020. However, there was a ban on discos, entertainment venues (nightclubs), catering establishments at night, which has high demand among young people.

On the eve of the Christmas and New Year holidays of 2021, quarantine restrictions were introduced on the conduct of festive events, workshops, public events in entertainment venues and restaurants. To prevent a new wave of disease during the New Year holidays and Christmas, from 8 to 24 January 2021, Ukraine is re-introducing lockdown (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020b), which prohibits the operation of theatres, shopping malls, cinemas, as leisure facilities, fitness clubs, swimming pools, gyms, etc.

From 25 January and throughout 2021, the work of cultural institutions and creative industries is regulated by restrictive anti-epidemic measures of adaptive quarantine, which provide for compliance with the established requirements: occupancy of cinemas, theatres up to 50%, the number of visitors to mass cultural/sporting events not more than 20, the number of visitors to fitness centres / gyms — one person per 20 square meters. m., at a distance of 1.5 meters, etc. (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2020b).

All regions of Ukraine entered the “green” level of epidemic security only on 17 June 2021. However, the Ukrainian government continued restrictive measures of adaptive quarantine and are currently in force until 31 March 2022, subject to the relevant epidemiological situation.

Thus, the Ukrainian state, responding to the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic, gradually developed a system of national and regional measures to prevent and spread it. At the same time, taking care of the population’s health, they did not propose a program to overcome (alleviate) the effects of quarantine for cultural and creative industries that did not provide tools to support them during this difficult period.

COVID-19 has been negatively affected by a significant number of public spheres in Ukraine and worldwide, including the tourism industry, recreation and hospitality, creative industries, i.e. those that provide more social interaction and physical location.

According to current Ukrainian legislation (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2010), creative industries are economic activities that add value to jobs through cultural (artistic) and / or creative expression. Their products and services result from individual creativity. These include: visual, performing, audio, audiovisual art; design; literature and publishing; new media and IT; architecture and urban planning; advertising, marketing and PR; libraries, archives and museums; folk arts and crafts.

As mentioned above and prohibitions, the restrictions prevented the resumption of full-fledged operation of cultural and creative industries, which lost in the first year of quarantine about \$3 billion in revenue (Vinokurov, 2020) and 300,000 jobs. Accord-

ing to the study (Moroz & Obraztsova, 2021), in 2020 among the sectors of the creative industry of Ukraine suffered the most film screenings (–70%), film and television distribution (–37%), publishing (–26% to –14%), museums (–26%), theatrical and concert sphere (from –12% to –5%) (8). Losses in income and labour force push the culture and creative industries to the level of 2010 (Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine, 2020, p. 2).

To draw the government’s attention to the problems caused by the pandemic in the entertainment industry and the organization of mass events, on 12 May 2020, the Stop Cultural Quarantine event took place in Ukraine (Kvitsinska, 2020). In more than 20 cities of Ukraine — Kyiv, Kharkiv, Lviv, Odesa, Chernihiv, Uzhgorod, Ternopil, Vinnytsia, Cherkasy, Poltava, Uman, Rivne, Mariupol, Kamiansk, Kremenchuh, Drohobych, Vyshgorod, Stryi, the event was held under the slogan “If they don’t hear, they will see us”. Hundreds of searchlights shone in the sky for several hours at well-known locations in these cities. See Figures 1.

Figure 1. Promeni aktsii #stopkulturalnyikarantyn [Rays of the #stopcultural quarantine action]. Kyiv. Ukraine. 12 May 2020. Photo (Sodel, 2020).

Such events demonstrate the national unity of citizens across the country with common social and cultural interests, encouraging such actions to social activity, especially youth, and their implementation of individual and collective creative ideas and solutions that could fill the existing leisure and information vacuum.

According to the UN, 16 % or 1.2 billion of the world’s population are young people aged 15–24 (UNESCO, 2020). The catastrophic consequences of the COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic have mobilized an active part of the youth community worldwide and focused their attention on the development of socially demanded social projects.

Educational and outreach work in the fight against fakes and misinformation is important in the new reality. For example, in South Africa, the Ndlovu Youth Choir, winner of the 2019 America’s Got Talent project, prepared, performed and recorded a musical composition with WHO advise on safety issues in the context of coronavirus (Wickramanayake, 2020). Video compositions published on Twitter have been supplemented and expanded by Dr Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, WHO’s Secretary-General.

In addition, representatives of youth organizations and young people gather on online platforms use digital media to provide truthful information and advice that debunk the widespread myth of the pandemic. Nelson Kwaje, a young man from South Sudan, made it one of his missions by starting the #211CHECK digital youth community and working under the hashtag #COVID19SS (Wickramanayake, 2020).

Inés Yabar from Peru helped create Makesense TV, a subscription-based service that regularly provides people with accurate and useful information about COVID-19 (Wickramanayake, 2020), as well as a coronavirus inquiry page for vulnerable communities.

The project The World Association of Girl Guides and Girl Scouts is worth noting, which develops and renews greenery in Beirut in Lebanon and surrounding areas. Its goal is to create safe places for citizens to rest during the pandemic (World Health Organization, 2021).

The presented projects are examples of participation of enterprising youth from all over the world in implementing measures to counter the spread of the pandemic, have a social dimension and contribute to the personal development of young developers-innovators. The WHO should establish and maintain contacts with gifted youth because “innovation is most valuable when it benefits everyone, especially the most vulnerable”, said Dr Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, Director-General of the World Health Organization (World Health Organization, 2021).

The National Youth Strategy until 2030 defines youth as an essential subject of public policy, which has the right to independently determine its own goals and values, show initiative, and participate in the development of the state. As of 1 January 2020, about 10.6 million young people aged 14 to 35 lived in Ukraine (President of Ukraine, 2021).

According to Report (Boiarko et al., 2019), Ukrainian youth is aware of the importance of obtaining a complete higher education for further successful employment. Kvit et al. (2020) reported that as of November 2019 in Ukraine, there were 671 higher education institutions, which is 16 per 1 million population of Ukraine (15). 1,322.3 thousand higher education students study at universities, institutes and academies (24).

At the same time, according to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine (Karmazina, 2018), there are 113 theatres, 76 concert organizations, 574 museums, 16.8 thousand libraries, 17.1 thousand clubs in Ukraine (9); 1302 art (22) and 1281 children's and youth sports schools (28). Thus, we can assume that the number of leisure facilities in Ukraine, as part of the creative industries, can meet the needs of modern youth.

We agree with Scraton and Watson (2016) that people most often use leisure for the lifestyle they most seek, so Ukrainian youth leisure activities logically fit into and are satisfied with the creative industries.

According to Haidai et al. (2017, p. 115), before the pandemic, Ukrainian youth preferred leisure among their life priorities, choosing to listen to music (77%), relax with family (71%), meet with friends in public (61%), etc. Among the popular types of leisure activities were also: watching movies (59%), playing sports (33%), reading books (23%), video games (18%). 16% of young people were engaged in creative and artistic work (playing musical instruments, writing poems, pottery, embroidery, graphic design, etc.) as a form of leisure.

In addition, Ukrainians spent a significant part of their free time on regular Internet use (almost 22.9 million people, 71% of the country's population), as evidenced by 2019 data. Adolescents and young people aged 15 to 24 accounted for 15% of users, and those aged 25–34 – 25% (Yatsenko, 2019, p. 9). The level of regular Internet users among pupils and students reached 97% (Nazarenko et al., 2020). The presented data indicate a wide range of leisure interests of modern Ukrainian youth in the pre-quarantine period.

The pandemic and forced quarantine have become a moral challenge for young people and have demonstrated the importance of cultural and creative industries and leisure in their lives. Closure of cinemas, clubs, discos, parks, sports complexes; the transfer of music, book and film festivals, the cancellation of concerts became a kind of “spring shock” and changed the structure of youth leisure, limiting it to home (private) space. The level of communication and personal contacts has decreased significantly, although the need for communication has not disappeared. In addition, in the first months of quarantine, 45.9% of young people experienced stress due to uncertainty and anxiety due to financial difficulties in the family, worries about the health of loved ones, etc., another 30.5% were depressed (Ostrikova et al., 2020).

According to Nazarenko et al. (2020, p. 30), Ukrainian youth understands leisure as a guarantee of mental health, a space for self-development; associates it with positive emotions; passive state to restore strength; socializing with friends/family. That is everything that happens at home. Leisure is associated as a component of creative activity, which is manifested through: hobbies, handicrafts, crafts; acquisition or improvement of skills; planned active recreation in public space (p. 31–32). That is, with the form of self-expression, human self-development.

As in pre-quarantine times, the most popular activities for young people at home in 2020 were the consumption of various content, such as: surfing the Internet (82%), listening to music (67%), watching videos (55%). Leisure activities such as reading, receiving or visiting guests, classes in the gym were used by 28%, 20% and 19% of young people, respectively (Nazarenko et al., 2020, pp. 24–25).

In response to young people's requests for self-development and learning, the Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine in early 2020 launched the National Online Digital Literacy Platform “Action. Digital education”. The purpose of the platform is to teach Ukrainians digital skills. Hence, educational series focusing on online safety are offered to parents and children; for adults with basic digital skills – specialized, in-depth courses, mastering new professions; for young people (schoolchildren and students) – courses in media literacy, entrepreneurship, new digital professions. For example, among the educational series for young people, we will name: “Media Literacy in Pandemic Times”, “Digital Journalism”, “Financial Sensei”. “Artificial Intelligence for Schoolchildren”, “Introduction: Digital Marketing for Schoolchildren and Students”, “On Cyberbullying for Adolescents” courses etc., were offered to schoolchildren and adolescents. The series “Digital Physical Education for schoolchildren with the participation of sports stars” became popular (it included sports at home during quarantine) (“Osvitni Serialy”, n.d.).

Training is conducted in the innovative format of the educational series: each course offers series instead of lessons, seasons instead of levels. The educational material is presented in dialogues between expert teachers and famous Ukrainian stars

of culture, sports, art, youth idols, etc. Depending on the topic, the series offers 5 to 12 series and ends with final tests. After a positive evaluation, participants receive certificates of completion of the chosen course and acquire new digital literacy skills.

Forced transition to distance work or study, the need for constant use of messengers, video communications for webinars, meetings, video conferences, increased consumption of large amounts of information and cultural products on the Internet, the emergence of applications for listening to music and watching movies and more. Thus, according to the GlobalLogic study, the number of Ukrainian Internet users has significantly increased during the quarantine year, reaching almost 30 million in early 2021. The number of Ukrainian users on social networks has also grown considerably: from 19 million in early 2020 to 26 million in 2021. The most popular social networks were YouTube (96% of users), followed by Instagram (14 million users) and Facebook (16 million) (Shtukaturova, 2021).

Traditionally, active recreation in nature is one of the favourite types of youth leisure, so improving the epidemic situation has stimulated the organization of independent travel in Ukraine (hiking, mountain routes, cycling). The holiday season in August 2020 and the Christmas and New Year holidays of 2021 also tended to increase foreign travel (Solonyna, 2021). However, among the problems that emerged during the pandemic, in addition to anxiety and stress, it is worth mentioning the blurring of the boundaries between work/study and leisure; irregular working hours (overtime), emotional burnout.

Therefore, we agree with Nesterovich (2020) that mass events in public space will become more restricted and controlled after the quarantine. Concerts, festivals, sports events will be transformed, forced, together with theatres, cinemas, orchestras, to reorganize activities following new challenges.

Yuri Lotman's (n.d.) famous quote — "Culture begins with prohibitions" — perfectly illustrates the background that stimulated the emergence of creative ideas and creative projects proposed during the pandemic in Ukraine.

Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts (KNUCA) is a leading institution of higher education in Ukraine for training in culture and arts. During the forced quarantine, university students developed and implemented interesting creative initiatives and demonstrated their own talents and ideas in various creative artistic and cultural projects described below.

In early May 2020, after almost two months of lockdown, members of the folk ensemble Kralytsia, which operates at the Faculty of Music KNUCA, launched on the social network Facebook All-Ukrainian challenge *#Lovynamysto*. The 2nd and 3rd-year students shot a video showing the moment of "transfer" from one participant to another — coral necklaces — traditional Ukrainian jewellery worn by women around their necks. Upon receiving the necklace, the participants appear in traditional Ukrainian attire. The Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts website states that the video received more than 1,000,000 views and 16,000 shares ("*#Lovynamysto: ponad*", 2020). In a short time, students and young people from different Ukrainian regions joined the challenge. Instagram channel *#sho_tam* (Sho_tam, 2020) called *#Lovynamysto* "the best quarantine challenge in Ukraine".

In early 2021, creative students of the Department of Fashion Business, Faculty of Event Management, Fashion and Show Business Kyiv National University of Cul-

ture and Arts initiated and conducted an interesting online project *Winter Magic Fest*, demonstrating creativity and vision to create winter images. During the month, unique, sometimes phantasmagoric images created in the categories “Fairytale Character” and “Party Look” (“Winter Magic Fest”, 2021) were presented on social networks. Thus, in the first category, the participants presented the heroes of their favourite movies and fairy tales with the help of make-up and clothes. The participants presented the full stylistic image for the New Year’s party in the second category. Also, in this block, it was necessary to offer festive make-up and original hairstyles for the cover of a glossy magazine. According to the jury, ten authors who presented the most original ideas of winter make-up received New Year’s gifts from the Estel brand.

During the second wave of quarantine, Halyna Pylypenko, a researcher at the Lesia Ukrainka Literary Memorial Museum, Novohrad-Volynskyi (2021), initiated the International Online Flashmob #GlobalLesyaUkrainka2021 on Facebook. The flash mob was organized to mark the 150th anniversary of the birth of the famous Ukrainian poet and translator Lesya Ukrainka and to review the memorable places of her stay in Ukraine and around the world.

Ukrainian universities, colleges, high school and junior high school students; public, youth and children’s libraries; departments of the culture of rural and urban communities; Ukrainians of all ages and social status actively participated in this flash mob during 2021. Participants took photos or selfies, recorded videos reading Lesya’s poetry near monuments, such as monuments, bas-reliefs, memorial plaques; on the streets/squares/boulevards named after her. All photos and videos are posted on Facebook with the hashtag # GlobalLesyaUkrainka2021. Indicators of coverage of the message for the year amounted to 290,997, interaction with the post — 28,587; the post received 2,300 shares. Residents of Ukraine, Georgia, Denmark, Hungary, Turkey, Lithuania, the USA, the Czech Republic, Germany, Poland, Israel and other countries took part in the flash mob (Lesia Ukrainka Literary Memorial Museum, Novohrad-Volynskyi, 2022).

Conclusions

The COVID-19 pandemic has become an unexpected global challenge, creating unprecedented solidarity, complicity, initiative, volunteerism, and partnership of people around the world. A brief overview showed that the best international experience of youth activities in response to the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic is realized mainly in the social dimension. In Ukraine, the rapid spread of SARS-CoV-2 has organized the population and demonstrated its ability to self-organize, jointly combat the spread of the disease, and at the same time influenced the search for new creative ideas of leisure by Ukrainian citizens of all ages, including young people.

As the realities and results of the study presented in this article have shown, culture and leisure have become the most vulnerable to the challenges of the pandemic. Although Ukraine has an extensive network of cultural, leisure, sports, creative industries, bans and restrictions on their work have led to a significant dominance of those leisure activities that are available at home: online communication, watching movies, listening to music, reading, creative work, etc.

The research focused on successful creative projects initiated by the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts students and supported by the public from different parts of Ukraine. The presented experience shows that talented Ukrainian youth does not stand aside from today's global challenges but initiates unique creative developments in a pandemic that promotes self-development, awareness of its role in state building, ability to generate creative ideas and develop unique, innovative ideas projects.

The advantage of the presented successful leisure practices of Ukrainian youth, including #*GlobalLesyaUkrainka2021* online flashmob, #*Lovynamysto*, *Winter Magic Fest* challenge, were developments taken from the rich potential of national cultural heritage, folk traditions, which due to modern digital technology, have become widespread within the country and can be useful for global leisure organizers.

The New Year and Christmas holidays of the end of 2021 and the beginning of 2022 in Ukraine became mass and allowed citizens to communicate inside the country and abroad actively. At present, it is challenging to predict the impact of new strains of coronavirus on human life and health, so we should not forget about the possibility of introducing new strict quarantine restrictions. Therefore, the proposed creative ideas for leisure in Ukraine remain relevant and can serve as a good idea for implementation in different parts of the world.

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ДОЗВІЛЛЯ МОЛОДІ ПІД ЧАС COVID-19: ТРИ ТВОРЧІ ВРАЖЕННЯ З УКРАЇНИ

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Мета статті — дослідити вплив пандемії COVID-19 на організацію дозвілля молоді в Україні. Методологія дослідження заснована на комплексному аналізі системи загальнодержавних заходів запобігання та поширення коронавірусної інфекції, впроваджених українським урядом; аналітичному, структурно-логічному та порівняльно-співставному методах, які дозволили провести огляд правового статусу, освітньої та дозвілєвої активності молоді в Україні, міжнародного досвіду участі молоді у соціальних проєктах протидії поширенню COVID-19; методі теоретичного узагальнення, що використаний для підбиття підсумків; культурологічному підході, за допомогою якого виявлено чинники впливу загальнодержавних заходів на діяльність секторів культурної та

креативної індустрії. Наукова новизна. Презентовано три креативні ініціативи української молоді щодо організації власного дозвілля, що започатковані в умовах локдауну та створені на основі багатого потенціалу національної культурної спадщини та народних традицій. Висновки. Українська держава, реагуючи на виклики пандемії COVID-19, виробила систему заходів щодо її запобігання. Попри велику кількість закладів дозвілля, спорту, креативних індустрій в Україні, карантинні обмеження та заборони, спричинені COVID-19, призвели до їх закриття, а молодь зосередилася на дозвіллі вдома, креативному саморозвитку та самоорганізації свого вільного часу. Визначено, що кращий міжнародний досвід молодіжної активності протидії викликам пандемії COVID-19 реалізується переважно у соціальному вимірі. Українська молодь не стоїть осторонь глобальних викликів сучасності, а ініціює унікальні творчі розробки в умовах пандемії. Представлено українські творчі ініціативи, серед яких онлайн-проект #GlobalLesyaUkrainka2021 та успішний досвід самоорганізації дозвілля студентською молоддю Київського національного університету культури і мистецтв (Челендж #Ловинамісто and Winter Magic Fest).

Ключові слова: COVID-19; дозвілля молоді; Україна; креативні проєкти, креативні індустрії

